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COMPARISON OF CONVENTIONAL -TYPE AND FUZZY- TYPE PID CONTROLLER

Ahamad Faras

Assistant Professor,
Shivdan Singh College,
Aligarh, U.P. India

Abstract:

The best known controllers used in the industries are the proportional - integral - derivative (PID) controller because of their simple structure and robust performance in wide operating conditions. But the performance of these controller get affected with parameters variation and with the increase in the complexity of the system After being mostly viewed as a controversial technology for two decades, fuzzy logic has finally been accepted as an emerging technology. This is largely due to a wide array of successful applications ranging from consumer products, to industrial process control, to automotive applications. Fuzzy systems are very useful in two general contexts: (1) in situations involving highly complex systems whose behaviors are not well understood, and (2) in situations where an approximate, but fast, solution is warranted. In this paper we have tried to compare the conventional PI and PD controller with fuzzy PI-like and PD like controller Simple control systems based on conventional and fuzzy technique are developed for basic transfer function that may occur in industries. Mamdani type Fuzzy inference system (FIS) is used .Comparison of two types of controller is done based on the response of plants with these controllers. It also shows which one is a better choice of the two type of controller for given system. This compression will make us capable to choose the batter control strategy for particular application.

Key words: Fuzzy Inference System (FIS), Fuzzy Logic, Mamdani, Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO)

I-INTRODUCTION

The best known controllers used in the industries are the proportional - integral - derivative (PID) controller because of their simple structure and robust performance in wide operating conditions. The PID controller is used for a wide range of problems like motor drives, automotive, flight control, instrumentation etc. PID controllers provide robust and reliable performance for most systems if the PID parameters are tuned properly. Because of the importance of PID controller we have

considered these controllers also we tried to compare PID controllers with fuzzy PI-like and PD-like controllers [15]. After being mostly viewed as a controversial technology for two decades, fuzzy logic has finally been accepted as an emerging technology since the late 1980s. This is largely due to a wide array of successful applications ranging from consumer products, to industrial process control, to automotive applications [7]. Fuzzy logic is closer in spirit to human thinking and natural language than conventional logical systems [8]. Classical control theory is based on the mathematical models that describe the physical plant

under consideration. The essence of fuzzy control is to build a model of human expert who is capable of controlling the plant without thinking in terms of mathematical model

[9]. In this report we have tried to compare the conventional PI and PD controller with fuzzy PI-like and PD like controller

II-CONVENTIONAL VS, FUZZY CONTROLLER

The primary requirement of any control system is to guarantee the closed-loop stability. In addition to possessing closed-loop stability, a control system must be designed to meet certain robustness and/or performance specifications. The PID controller is the most widely used structure in industrial applications. This prevalence of the PID controller is due to its simplicity of controller structure and ability to solve many practical control problems [12].

A PID controller structure is selected to control the system as it is easy and intuitive to tune. It is also used extensively in the industry [13] and there is a benefit of using a well-known and trusted controller in future applications. This is a simple and desirable solution, since it does not require new control algorithms, just new tunings to fit for the varying delay. With a more complex controller the delay could be explicitly taken into account in the control algorithm, and better results could be possible. With a PID controller adequate performance can be achieved. The transfer function of the PID controller looks like the following:

$$\frac{U(s)}{E(s)} = (K_p + K_i / s + sK_d) \quad (2.1)$$

Where K_p = Proportional gain , K_i = Integral gain

K_d = Derivative gain

$$e(t) = r(t) - y(t) \quad (2.2)$$

Fuzzy logic is a class of Artificial intelligence [16], but its history and applications are more recent than expert system. In 1965, Lotfy Zadeh, a computer scientist, propounded the theory of fuzzy

logic. He argued that human thinking is often fuzzy, vague, or imprecise in nature and, therefore, cannot be represented by yes (1) or no (0) type precision logic used in expert system. While both expert system and fuzzy logic are rule based, the latter is basically based on multivalued logic (between 0 and 1). Fuzzy logic controllers (FLC) are based on fuzzy logic theory and employ a method of approximate reasoning that resembles the decision making process of humans. The behavior of a FLC is easily understood by a human expert, as knowledge is expressed by means of intuitive, linguistic rules. In contrast with traditional linear and nonlinear control theory, a FLC is not based on a mathematical model and is widely used to solve problems under uncertain and vague environments, with high nonlinearities. In contrast with traditional linear and nonlinear control theory, a FLC is not based on a mathematical model and is widely used to solve problems under uncertain and vague environments

In this section, numerical studies are conducted to examine the performance of fuzzy PID controllers. Three examples are studied using Matlab's Fuzzy logic Toolbox. The Range-Kutta method is used for all simulations. A unit step response is studied to simulate set point control. A fixed step type is used and sampling time is set at 0.01 s. After the implementation of control system a simple analysis is made based on conventional control theory to verify the design.

III-COMPARISON OF TWO CONTROLLERS

Example 1, A First-Order Process with time delay: Many industrial processes such as temperature, pressure, and fluid-level control, can be approximated by a first-order model [11]. A three term model of a first order process is generally given by

$$G(s) = \frac{k}{t_c s + 1} e^{-t_d s} \quad (1)$$

where t_c , t_d and k are time constant , time delay and study state gain of the plant respectively. The time delay occurs when

a sensor and an actuator are installed with a physical separation. The process parameters in (1) are chosen as

$$t_c = 1 \quad t_d = 0.03 \quad K = 1, \text{ the transfer function is given as}$$

$$G(s) = \frac{1}{s+1} e^{-0.03s}$$

Figure:1- Simulink block diagram of plant with PI controller

Table-1

e \ ce	NL	NM	NS	Z	PS	PM	PL
NL	NL	NL	NL	NL	NM		Z
NM	NL	NL	NL	NM	NS	Z	PS
NS	NL	NL	NM	NS	Z	PS	PM
Z	NL	NM	NS	Z	PS	PM	PL
PS	NM	NS	Z	PS	PM	PL	PL
PM	NS	Z	PS	PM	PL	PL	PL
PL	Z	PS	PM	PL	PL	PL	PL

membership function is made, 7 membership value Negative large, Negative medium, Negative small, Positive small, Positive medium Positive large (NL, NM, NS, Z, PS, PM, PL) have been taken for PI like controller the two input are error (e) and change in error (ce) and out put is change in output of controller (cu) rang of input and output are in rang [-1 1]. Rule for the controller is shown Table-1. Figure-3 give rule surface for Fuzzy PI controller. Particle swan optimization is used for optimize tuning of controllers. When we run these two controller configuration and tune for better sating the result are as shown in Table-2. Graph in figure 4. is step response of conventional PI controller and figure 5 is for fuzzy PI like controller .

Figure-3. Rule surface for Mamdani type Fuzzy PI controller

Example 2, A Second-Order Process with over-damping:

$$G(s) = \frac{2}{s^2 + 4s + 3}$$

Figure 2 -Simulink block diagram of plant with fuzzy PI like controller

Figure 1 is the simulink block diagram of plant with simple PI controller and figure -2 is simulink block diagram of plant with fuzzy PI like controller For fuzzy PI-like controller the Mamdani type FIS was used , for simplicity the use of triangular

Many temperature control plant can also be modeled by a second order process with over-damping. The second example is a process with a transfer function of Now the plant in block diagram of figure 1 and 2 is second order system given above, when we run this simulink models of plant applying step in put and tune gain of the controllers with PSO, to find a better response the time response of the system with conventional and fuzzy controller is given by figure-6 & 7 respectively . Table 3 gives the

comparison of two controllers for given second order system

Figure:4-Step responses with PI controller Example-1

Figure.-5 Step responses with Fuzzy PI controller with Mamdani FIS in Example-1

Table-2

Performance Comparison in Example-1		
	Fuzzy PI-like	PI
Kp, Ki, Su	9, 0.69, 3.3	10.02 , 12.15, 1
Tr	0.167	0.135
Ts	0.33	0.25
POS (%)	8.8	1.39
PUS (%)	15.4	0

Figure.-6 Step responses with PI controller in Example-2

Figure.-7 Step responses with fuzzy PI controller with Mamdani type FIS in Example-2

Example: 3 A higher order Process: In this example we have used a higher order system with transfer function

$$G(s) = \frac{10}{s^3 + 6s^2 + 8s}$$

Table-3

Performance Comparison in Example-2		
	Fuzzy PI-like	PI
Kp, Ki, ,Su	0.9, 0.012, 6	4, 3.1, 1
Tr	0.872	0.64
Ts	2.35	2.96
POS (%)	4	7.1
PUS (%)	9.7	2.9

Figure.-8 Step responses with PD controller for Example 3

Simulink block diagram of the system with PD controller will be the same as in figure 1, but pi controller was replaced by PD controller. Also the block diagram of system will be the same as figure-2 with PI Like fuzzy controller is replaced by PD like fuzzy controller . When we run these models and adjust its gain for better responses then the output produced is given in the figure 8 for conventional PD controller. Next figure-9 is the block diagram of the system with fuzzy PD-like controller. . The gain of the three scheme and parameters of the system with these two controllers scheme is given in table-4.

Figure.-9 Step responses with fuzzy PD controller for Example-3

Table 4

Performance Comparison in Example-3		
	Fuzzy PD like	PD
K_p, K_d, S_u	0.4, 11, 19	2.5, 2.55, 1
Tr	0.805	0.503
Ts	1.58	1.58
POS (%)	6.1	9.8
PUS (%)	5.5	8.0

Conclusion

The comparison result shows that for example -1 PI controller gives the better performance than fuzzy PI like controller as the rise time, settling time, and peak overshoot for PI controller is less than the fuzzy PI-like controller. For second order system with delay of example-2 fuzzy PI-like controller gives better performance than PI controller as the rise time and settling time of fuzzy-PI like controller is less than the PI Like controller. However the peak overshoot of fuzzy PI-like controller is more but in permissible limit. In third case where the plant is a third order system the performance of fuzzy controller is best. From the above result it is concluded that for complex and higher order system the performance of fuzzy controller is better than the conventional PID controllers

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